

Radiomic reliability assessed on anatomical and diffusion MRI in Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD) patients

Lussana Francesca¹, Lanzarone Ettore¹, Villa Giulia², Mastropietro Alfonso³, Caroli Anna², Scalco Elisa⁴

¹ Department of Management, Information and Production Engineering, University of Bergamo, Dalmine (BG), Italy

² Medical Imaging Unit, Bioengineering Department, IRCCS Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri, Bergamo, Italy

³ Institute Of Intelligent Industrial Technologies and Systems, Italian National Research Council (STIIMA-CNR), Milan, Italy

⁴ Institute of Biomedical Technologies, Italian National Research Council (ITB-CNR), Segrate (MI), Italy

INTRODUCTION:

Autosomal Dominant Polycystic Kidney Disease (ADPKD) is a hereditary disorder characterized by fluid-filled cyst development [1], in which non-cystic tissue is an indicator of peritubular interstitial fibrosis, impacting renal function and its decline [2]. Radiomics has been recently proposed for classification and prediction of ADPKD stage and progression [3,4,5], but suffers from robustness and stability issues. Our study, which is part of a larger project [6], aims to propose a novel framework to identify reproducible and reliable radiomic features in characterizing non-cystic tissue via multi-parametric MRI (mp-MRI), which integrates anatomical images (T1-w, T2-w) and diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI). Three segmentation approaches for non-cystic tissue, from manual to automatic, were studied as a key source of variability. We suggest a new evaluation of radiomic reliability relying on reproducible and informative features.

METHODS:

Figure 1: Example of images (T1-w, T2-w and b0) and parametric maps (D, f and D*)

The dataset included 14 ADPKD patients from a prospective longitudinal clinical study (EuroCYST Initiative). Only data from Istituto di Ricerche Farmacologiche Mario Negri IRCCS, Bergamo, Italy were considered. Images were acquired with no contrast media injection following the protocol of the

Consortium for Radiologic Imaging Studies of Polycystic Kidney Disease (CRISP) [7]. An example of MRI acquisitions is reported in the first row of Figure 1.

T1-w and T2-w images pre-processing included bias fields correction [8] and intensity normalization [9].

Affine registration was computed between anatomical and DWI images and between b-values using Elastix [10].

IVIM parametric maps (D , f and D^*) were derived from DWI images through a supervised fully connected deep neural network (DNN) [11], trained on simulated signals. Resulting maps are depicted in the second row of Figure 1.

Non-cystic tissue was segmented using three methods: manual Ground Truth (GT), a Deep Learning network for cysts identification [12] (DLstart) on T2-w and obtaining the non-cystic region by subtracting the cystic tissue from the total kidney volume, and a post-processed version of it (DLadj) by removing vessel, fat and hemorrhagic cysts with mp-MRI. Agreement with manual GT was quantified using the Dice index.

92 radiomic features were extracted using Pyradiomics software [13] on each image and segmentation method, considering the two kidneys separately.

Radiomic feature reliability was assessed across different non-cystic segmentation computing Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC), employing the two-way mixed effect model, single rater type formulation [14]. Following Bologna et al. [15], reproducible radiomic features ($ICC > 0.8$) maintained consistency across regions of interest (ROIs) with similar information content (GT and DLadj), while informative features ($ICC < 0.5$) varied between ROIs with different content (GT and DLstart). Subsequently, the percentage of reliable features for each image type was determined.

RESULTS:

Segmentation results on T2-w in Figure 2 showed the DLadj segmentation closer to the GT compared to DLstart. Dice scores revealed stronger agreement between DLadj and GT (Dice = 0.69 ± 0.08) compared to DLstart and GT (Dice = 0.51 ± 0.11). Radiomic reliability shown in Table 1 highlighted higher reliability for DLadj segmentation, notably for IVIM maps ($ICC > 0.8$). DLadj exhibited lower reproducibility for T1-w and T2-w images, while DLstart demonstrated higher ICC values for these images.

Figure 2: Results of non-cystic segmentation using the different methods, showed on T2-w image

		GT	DL _{start}	DL _{adj}
<i>f</i>	GT	1.00	0.28	0.86
	DL _{start}	0.28	1.00	0.28
	DL _{adj}	0.86	0.28	1.00
<i>D</i>	GT	1.00	0.26	0.81
	DL _{start}	0.26	1.00	0.30
	DL _{adj}	0.81	0.30	1.00
<i>D*</i>	GT	1.00	0.41	0.89
	DL _{start}	0.41	1.00	0.43
	DL _{adj}	0.89	0.43	1.00
T2-w	GT	1.00	0.61	0.49
	DL _{start}	0.61	1.00	0.69
	DL _{adj}	0.49	0.69	1.00
T1-w	GT	1.00	0.70	0.51
	DL _{start}	0.70	1.00	0.40
	DL _{adj}	0.51	0.40	1.00

Table 1: ICC values averaged across all the radiomics features for *D*, *f*, *D**, T1-w and T2-w images

Figure 3 shows the percentage of reliable feature for each image, grouped by radiomic feature classes. The most reliable features are FO and GLCM for *D* and *f* parametric maps, as well as NGTDM for *D* parametric map and GLSZM for *f* map, with T1-w and T2-w images showing lower reliability.

Figure 3: Percentage of reliable features for D, f, D*, T1-w and T2-w images, divided for radiomic classes

DISCUSSION:

This study pioneers radiomic reliability assessment in non-cystic tissue of ADPKD patients using mp-MRI. Radiomics extracted from IVIM parametric maps offers an improved ability to assess micro-structural tissue organization and composition compared to standard T1-w and T2-w scans. Radiomic features shows reliability for D and f maps, moderacy for D* maps, and unreliability for T1-w and T2-w. Texture information from diffusion and flowing fraction maps effectively characterizes the non-cystic parenchymal region, providing both informative and resilient to minor segmentation discrepancies, mostly within the FO and GLCM feature classes. On the contrary, the low contrast among tissues in T1-w and T2-w images makes them unreliable for non-cystic characterization. A limitation of our study is the small sample size, prompting future validation in a larger, diverse population and exploration of correlations with clinical data on renal function for enhanced clinical utility.

CONCLUSION:

Our study highlights the robustness and reliability of radiomic features extracted from D and f IVIM maps in analyzing non-cystic kidney parenchyma in ADPKD patients, contrary to anatomical images that lack the required informativeness.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Caroli, A., Antiga, L., Conti, S., Sonzogni, A., Fasolini, G., Ondei, P., Perico, N., Remuzzi, G., Remuzzi, A.: Intermediate volume on computed tomography imaging defines a fibrotic compartment that predicts glomerular filtration rate decline in autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease patients. *The American Journal of Pathology* 179(2), 619–627 (2011)
- [2] Caroli, A., Kline, T.L.: Abdominal imaging in adpkd: Beyond total kidney volume. *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 12(15), 5133 (2023)
- [3] Xie, Y., Xu, M., Chen, Y., Zhu, X., Ju, S., Li, Y.: The predictive value of renal parenchymal information

- for renal function impairment in patients with adpkd: a multicenter prospective study. *Abdominal Radiology* 47(8), 2845–2857 (2022)
- [4] Kline, T.L., Korfiatis, P., Edwards, M.E., Bae, K.T., Yu, A., Chapman, A.B., Mrug, M., Grantham, J.J., Landsittel, D., Bennett, W.M., et al.: Image texture features predict renal function decline in patients with autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease. *Kidney International* 92(5), 1206–1216 (2017)
- [5] Li, X., Liu, Q., Xu, J., Huang, C., Hua, Q., Wang, H., Ma, T., Huang, Z.: A mri-based radiomics nomogram for evaluation of renal function in adpkd. *Abdominal Radiology* 47(4), 1385–1395 (2022)
- [6] AI-based methods to improve stratification of patients affected by Polycystic Kidney Disease using multi-parametric MRI – AI4PKD", grant protocol number 2022B23JT5, call PRIN 2022 (DD MUR n. 104, 02.02.2022), funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research and the European Union – Next generation EU (PNRR M4.C2.1.1)
- [7] Chapman, A.B., Guay-Woodford, L.M., Grantham, J.J., Torres, V.E., Bae, K.T., Baumgarten, D.A., Kenney, P.J., King Jr, B.F., Glockner, J.F., Wetzel, L.H., et al.: Renal structure in early autosomal-dominant polycystic kidney disease (adpkd): The consortium for radiologic imaging studies of polycystic kidney disease (crisp) cohort. *Kidney International* 64(3), 1035–1045 (2003)
- [8] Tustison, N.J., Avants, B.B., Cook, P.A., Zheng, Y., Egan, A., Yushkevich, P.A., Gee, J.C.: N4itk: improved n3 bias correction. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 29(6), 1310–1320 (2010)
- [9] Ný ul, L.G., Udupa, J.K., Zhang, X.: New variants of a method of mri scale standardization. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 19(2), 143–150 (2000)
- [10] Klein, S., Staring, M., Murphy, K., Viergever, M.A., Pluim, J.P.: Elastix: a toolbox for intensity-based medical image registration. *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging* 29(1), 196–205 (2009)
- [11] Mastropietro, A., Procissi, D., Scalco, E., Rizzo, G., Bertolino, N.: A supervised deep neural network approach with standardized targets for enhanced accuracy of ivim parameter estimation from multi-snr images. *NMR in Biomedicine* 35(10), e4774 (2022)
- [12] Kline, T.L., Edwards, M.E., Fetzer, J., Gregory, A.V., Anaam, D., Metzger, A.J., Erickson, B.J.: Automatic semantic segmentation of kidney cysts in mr images of patients affected by autosomal-dominant polycystic kidney disease. *Abdominal Radiology* 46, 1053–1061 (2021)
- [13] Van Griethuysen, J.J., Fedorov, A., Parmar, C., Hosny, A., Aucoin, N., Narayan, V., Beets-Tan, R.G., Fillion-Robin, J.C., Pieper, S., Aerts, H.J.: Computational radiomics system to decode the radiographic phenotype. *Cancer Research* 77(21), e104–e107 (2017)
- [14] Koo, T.K., Li, M.Y.: A guideline of selecting and reporting intraclass correlation coefficients for reliability research. *Journal of Chiropractic Medicine* 15(2), 155–163 (2016)
- [15] Bologna, M., Corino, V.D., Montin, E., Messina, A., Calareso, G., Greco, F.G., Sdao, S., Mainardi, L.T.: Assessment of stability and discrimination capacity of radiomic features on apparent diffusion coefficient images. *Journal of Digital Imaging* 31, 879–894 (2018)